

We are the authors of the bioRxiv preprint “A robust receptive field code for optic flow detection and decomposition during self-motion (doi: [10.1101/2021.10.06.463330](https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.10.06.463330)). Here are our responses to the community review by Arthur Zhao (doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5797244](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5797244)).

Zhang et al applied a previous developed method (Zhang and Arrenberg 2019) to identify and characterize the receptive fields of many motion-sensitive neurons in zebrafish. They found that some of these neurons behave as “matched filters” (detecting a single motion) and robustly encode translation-induced optic flows. The anatomical arrangement of these neurons in the brain seemed to correlate with their motion sensitivity. The authors also conducted behavior experiments to show that the fish is capable of decompose the translational and rotational components of a mixed optic flow.

Using visual information to infer self-motion is a crucial task for animals’ survival. The methods and findings in the manuscript would be of general interest to the motion-vision community. The manuscript is clearly written with detailed method description. Some comments and questions are listed below:

1. The contiguous motion noise (CMN) stimulus and the accompanied statistical methods developed by the authors are quite interesting and seem to work well identifying neurons with small receptive fields (correlation length of the stimulus). However, matched filters that encode self-motion tend to have large receptive field (looking at the background motion). Are we missing most of the “rotation neurons” (there seem to be 60 rotation complex RF but not much analysis on them)? Should we expect other translation neurons with much larger RF? Have the authors tried CMN with large correlation lengths?

We decided to only focus on the translation RF neurons but not rotation neurons not only because they are much fewer, but their responses to mixed optic flow (but not pure translation/rotation optic flow) are less predictable by their RFs as linear filter than translation RFs as shown in Figure S2D. This makes the rotation RF neurons not suitable for the linear analysis in Figure 4-6. We added line 230-233 to clarify this problem:

“Translation neurons were more abundant than rotation neurons and their responses to combinations of optic flow were more predictable with the matched filter model (Figure S2D), suggesting that additional unknown stimulus features modulate the responses of rotation neurons. In the following, we will mainly focus on the population properties of the translation RFs. “

It is possible that we may find rotation RF neurons outside of the optic tectum and pretectal area whose optic flow responses might be more linear, and it would be interesting to know what role they play in the optic flow transformation process if these neurons exist.

Due to the hardware and RF estimation method limitations in this study, it is possible that the number of the translation neurons with “extra-large” RFs is underestimated. The determination of the exact RF diameter is one of the things that are very difficult to

accomplish with our method, given that the stimulus always contained locally-coherent motion. Thus, this may not be solved with using larger contiguous radius CMN, as this may result in a poorer estimation of RF size. It could be improved with longer RF estimation protocol which unfortunately could not be accomplished in this study because of the memory limit of the microprocessors for the LED arena we used.

2. Out of the 400 complex RF, are they all different given that they are from 7 fish? Can we estimate how many, say, translation sensitive motion neurons are in one fish (maybe also from Figure 4A)?

We found 47 ± 25.2 (mean \pm std.) translation RFs per fish, which is $8.2\% \pm 3.2\%$ of the total number of RFs estimated per fish. In most fish, these translation RF neurons are located in the AMC cluster (see below, each dot indicate the anatomical location of a translation neuron):

3. The fact that unimodal and bimodal neurons are mostly located in different parts of the brain suggests to me the bimodal neurons could be downstream (integrator) of the unimodal ones. In other words, could the unimodal neurons encode all the visual information seen in the complex ones? If this were the case, it should've been made clear before making comparisons between the complex and simple RFs (eg. Line222). To be clear, I do think it's instructional to applies the same analysis to both sets of neurons.

We added line 505-508 to speculate that the bimodal neurons are the downstream of the unimodal neurons:

“Most complex RFs are bimodal RFs (Figure 3B) and it is possible that the bimodal RFs of these neurons are inherited from pairs of presynaptic unimodal RF neurons³², which may be confirmed by systematic connectivity characterization in the future.”

If this is the case, then the visual information encoded by the population of unimodal neurons should definitely contain all information encoded by the population of bimodal neurons. However, this relationship only exists at **population level**, for unimodal vs. complex RF neurons, but not unimodal vs. bimodal RF neurons.

In line 222 (line 219 in the current version), we compared the simple RFs with complex RFs, but not unimodal vs. bimodal:

“The average correlation for the neurons with complex RFs (0.81) was higher than the correlation for the neurons with simple RFs (0.65), which means that the complex RFs on average gave better prediction of the neural responses to optic flow stimuli than the simple RFs (Figure 3F and S2D).”

Here we showed the complex RF neurons' responses are more predictable by the linear model than simple RF neurons at **individual neuron level**. The question of connectivity is interesting though and should be investigated further.

4. I'm not convinced by the “topographic arrangement” shown in Figure 4B. Do the author mean “retinotopy” or something much weaker? There is clearly a left-right separation in 4B, but that's not retinotopy, at least not clear from those neurons.

To address this issue, we performed the point-reflection of the left cluster with respect to the origin to the right (Figure S4G), so the left and right AMC clusters are combined for determining the intra-cluster Pearson's correlation for anatomical location and preferred translation direction. The Pearson's correlation is 0.29 ($p < 0.001$), showing that a weak, but significant topography. We have also added a binned plot of the topography at the bottom of panel 4B for better visualization and add lines 269-273:

“Linear regression showed that the preferred translation direction is strongly correlated with anatomical position ($R^2 = 0.73$, Figure S4F), and that topography is weaker, but still present, when removing the effects of left-right hemisphere organization (correlation = 0.29, Figure S4G).”

5. The distribution of translation directions in Figure 4A looks interesting. Could the authors comment on the ethological aspect? Do we expect this distribution given how the fish swim and navigate?

The non-uniform translation direction distribution in Figure 4A could be resulted by at least two factors: the naturalistic optic flow statistics and the statistics of zebrafish larvae locomotor behaviour. The naturalistic optic flow statistics includes the visual scene statistic and the statistics of the processes that lead to passive self-motion (e.g. turbulence). The former can be characterized from naturalistic videos collected from zebrafish's nature habitat, and we are already working on this. The latter and fish's natural locomotor behavioural statistic is harder to measure and characterize. And before proving any of these, one needs to test if the translation direction distribution is affected by the genetic background of the transgenic fish, as in this study, we only used one transgenic line (mpn400).

6. The behavior experiments are clever, but it feels a bit open-ended and could use some more analysis. In Figure 6E, the eye motion seems to be monotonic during the 20s stimulus. Is this by design? What happens if the stimulus is longer? For the T+R mixture case, the motion range of the right eye is much smaller and have the negative sign (comparing to the

first 3 cases). Does this mean the right eye is trying to move leftwards and limited by the binocular region? If so, does it mean the fish is trying to follow the dominate (faster) stimulus on its left side.

As illustrated in Figure 6B and specified in the corresponding figure legend, the fast saccadic eye movements are removed as we are only interested in the OKR-related slow phases. So the raw eye motions are not monotonic as the eye positions are often reset by the fast saccades when they reach the limits.

We agree it will be interesting and useful to characterize the degree of decomposition, and we have tried this in the past. However, with the current experiment design and hardware, it is hard to find reliable and appropriate objective measures for this task. One major challenge is to distinguish the translation- and rotation-induced components from the OKR and OMR behaviour, which may require the knowledge of the complete sensorimotor transformation of optic flow in zebrafish.

Naively I'd expect the fish to be able to disentangle translation from rotation to a certain degree. There will always be ambiguous cases. It'll be useful to know the fish's limit in decomposing mixed motions. Finally, in the abstract, the author mentioned "predicted decomposition in OKR and OMR". It sounds as if it's possible to predict how mixed motion is decomposed, which is not the case based on my understanding.

In Figure 3, we showed the complex RF neuron responses to optic flow can be well explained by their complex RF as linear filter. The implementation of this linear filter model will result in the decomposition of translational and rotational information in the neural responses, which can be proven mathematically. This segregation has been observed in Video S1 and S2 where the rotation interference in the mixed optic flow showed no noticeable effect on the population responses of AMC. And this is further supported by Figure 5A that the translation information encoded by the translation-sensitive neuron population are not corrupted or biased by the rotational component in the mixed optic flow. Based on these evidences, it was predicted the segregation of translation and rotation information observed at neural correlate level should also be observed at behavioural level. The reasoning has been briefly mentioned in the summary:

"The unambiguous encoding of translation enables the decomposition of translational and rotational self-motion information from mixed optic flow."

The very last sentence in the abstract is also a too strong statement, I believe, since we don't really know the algorithm nor the circuit yet.

The "algorithm" which we identified is manifested in the complex RFs of individual neurons. This matched filter algorithm shows how self-motion information is extracted at the single cell level. We agree though that additional investigation is needed to identify how these neurons are connected with each other at the circuit level to establish the perception of self-motion for the animal and/or to drive stabilization behavior.

Some minor points

1. Figure 4C, the y-axis is confusing. Are 180 and -180 not the same?

Yes, they are the same, they are labelled and plotted in such way so we can show the linear correlation of circular variable. In addition, we have now moved Figure 4C to supplementary figures (Figure S4F).

2. Figure 5D, y-axis should have no unit

We have fixed the issue in our current version.

3. Figure 6C, for the swim trajectories, I think showing one example would be much clearer. Adding all the trajectories just make it hard to see the red one (the blue ones are intelligible).

We agree and the individual trajectories have been plotted in Figure S6B.